

Pauli Exclusion Principle Turns 100 Years Old

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SUMMARY

The Pauli exclusion principle states that two identical fermions cannot occupy the same quantum state simultaneously within a quantum system. This means that there cannot be two electrons with the same set of quantum numbers in a given atom, which directly affects the electronic configuration of the atoms and therefore the chemical properties of the elements. Furthermore, the Pauli exclusion principle has significant implications for a variety of physical and astrological phenomena, including the stability of matter, the properties of conductors and insulators, and the structure and evolution of stars, including white dwarfs and neutron stars.

Keywords: Pauli, Fermions, Matter Stability, Exclusion Principle

BRIEF PAULI BIOGRAPHY

According to ENZ ⁽¹⁾, Wolfgang Ernst Friedrich Pauli was considered by Albert Einstein himself to be his successor. Pauli was born on April 25, 1900 in Vienna, Austria, to Wolfgang Josef Pascheles and Bertha Camilla Schütz. Wolfgang Pascheles studied medicine with Ludwig, the eldest son of the famous physicist Ernst Mach, who was a professor of experimental physics and greatly influenced Pauli's personality and his taste for physics and

Received: 2 November 2024

Revised: 22 November 2024

Accepted: 27 November 2024

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DOI: [HTTPS://DOI.ORG/10.5281/ZENODO.14227195](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14227195)

mathematics. The great friendship and consideration that Josef Pascheles had for the Austrian physicist and philosopher Ernst Mach led him to invite him to be the godfather of his son Wolfgang Pauli and honor him with the middle name being Ernst, the name Friedrich was also a tribute to his grandfather Friedrich Schütz, father of his mother Bertha Camila Schütz, Pascheles' first wife, with whom he had two children, Wolfgang Ernst Friedrich Pauli and Hertha Ernestina Pauli, curious fact that the middle name Ernestina, was also a tribute to Ernest Mach.

In 1921, Pauli defended his thesis on the investigation of the ion of the hydrogen molecule, a milestone in the Bohr-Sommerfeld quantum theory, and with it he received his doctorate degree from the University of Munich. It was during this time that Pauli made great friends, one of them being Werner Karl Heisenberg, who was also Sommerfeld's student. This friendship lasted throughout his life. Between 1921 and 1922, Pauli was an assistant to Max Born in Göttingen. It was during this period that Pauli received an invitation from the famous Danish scientist Niels Bohr to spend a year working with him in Copenhagen, with great success. Pauli was awarded the Nobel Prize in 1929, on the recommendation of none other than Albert Einstein, for his work on the exclusion principle, commonly called the Pauli exclusion principle, which reveals the existence of the fourth quantum number, Spin.

Some interesting facts about Pauli indicate that he had a very busy bohemian life. His mother Bertha committed suicide in 1927, which influenced him to abandon Catholicism and drink more often. Pauli married twice, his first marriage was to cabaret dancer Käthe Deppner in 1929, and it did not last a year.

QUANTUM ATOMIC MODEL

Many scientists contributed to the development of quantum mechanics, which attempts to explain the "most real" structure of an atom by combining several studies and, therefore, is the most complex.

The quantum atom model dates back to 1926. In this model, the nucleus is formed by protons and neutrons. The electrons form an electron cloud around the nucleus and move in orbitals in a three-dimensional space, and therefore their exact position cannot be defined. The orbitals are associated with calculations that determine the "probability of the region in which an electron will be at a given time".

Figure 1 - Representation of the quantum atomic model

Quantum Mechanics tells us that each electron in an atom can be associated with a set of values referring to the four quantum numbers, which determine the position occupied by the electron, the orientation in which it performs its rotation and the orbital. However, there is a restriction on the values that these numbers can have. This restriction is known as the “Pauli Exclusion Principle”, which states that two electrons in an atom can never have all four quantum numbers the same.

In this way, the values of the four quantum numbers can be assigned to each electron in an atom, according to the preceding rules, observing the Pauli Exclusion Principle.

It is possible to predict the probable location of an electron inside an atom through a mathematical set of values called quantum numbers.

i) PRINCIPAL QUANTUM NUMBER (n)

The principal quantum number (n) represents the atomic shell in which the electron is located. Its values are positive integers, and are experimentally determined with a range from 1 to 7. This number represents the average distance of the electron in relation to the nucleus of the atom, therefore, the higher the value of n, the further away the electron will be.

ii) AZIMUTHAL QUANTUM NUMBER (l)

The azimuthal quantum number (l) represents the subshell, that is, the shape of the orbital. It can have integer values from zero to n-1. When $l = 0$, there is the s subshell and a symmetrically spherical shape for the orbital, $l = 1$ designates a p subshell and an orbital

presenting a typical two-lobed shape of a p orbital. Similarly, $l = 2$ represents a d subshell and $l = 3$ a f subshell.

iii) MAGNETIC QUANTUM NUMBER (m_l)

The term magnetic refers to the fact that the orbitals of a given subshell have different quantized energies in the presence of a magnetic field. The value of this quantum number provides information about the orientation of an orbital in space. For the s subshell it has a value of zero, for the p subshell it can assume integer values in the range from -1 to $+1$, for the d subshell values from -2 to $+2$ and for the f subshell values from -3 to $+3$.

iv) SPIN QUANTUM NUMBER (m_s)

The fourth quantum number, often simply called spin, represents the axis of rotation of the electron in the orbital. It has values of $+1/2$ and $-1/2$, the first being attributed to a counterclockwise rotation and the second to a clockwise rotation.

Thus, these four quantum numbers complement each other and allow us to describe quite completely the behavior of electrons in atoms, including the electron's main energy level, the subenergy level, the spatial orientation of the electron cloud and the orientation of the electron itself in the cloud. Each combination of the four quantum numbers is unique for an electron. Quantum numbers correspond to eigenvalues of operators that commute with the Hamiltonian, that is, they can be measured at the same time as the energy of the total system. Furthermore, they are described in discrete values, assuming only a set of integer values, which are what make the energies of a given system quantized.

Name	Symbol	Specified Characteristic	Information Provided	Possible Values
Principal	n	Shell	Mean Distance from Nucleus	1, 2, 3, 4,...
Azimuthal	l	Subshell	Orbital Shape	0, 1, 2,...(n-1)
Magnético	m_l	Orbital	Orbital Orientation	-l, (-l+1),...0,...(l-1), l
Spin	m_s	Spin	Spin	-1/2, +1/2

Table 1 Values for the four quantum numbers

PAULI EXCLUSION PRINCIPLE

Firstly, it would be appropriate to emphasize that the topic in question, which deals with the Pauli exclusion principle, is addressed in most quantum mechanics textbooks. That

is, the topic is covered by a multitude of bibliographical references. It was through research into several of these books and texts that the article was produced. In particular, it is suggested that the following authors cited in the references be consulted: GRIFFITHS ⁽⁸⁾, LIBOFF ⁽⁹⁾, TIPLER ⁽¹⁰⁾, KAPLAN ⁽¹¹⁾, MESSIAH ⁽¹²⁾, LANDAU ⁽¹³⁾.

The Pauli exclusion principle states that two identical fermions cannot occupy the same quantum state simultaneously within a quantum system. This means that two electrons with the same set of quantum numbers cannot exist in a given atom, which directly affects the electron configuration of the atoms and therefore the chemical properties of the elements.

It is crucial to understanding the organization of electrons in atoms, which in turn determines how atoms bond to form molecules and how these materials have various physical and chemical properties. This principle applies not only to electrons (which are fermions), but also to other particles with half-integer spin, including quarks and neutrinos. Furthermore, the Pauli exclusion principle has significant implications for a variety of physical and astrophysical phenomena, including the stability of matter, the properties of conductors and insulators, and the structure and evolution of stars, including white dwarfs and neutron stars.

Understanding this principle is essential not only for physicists and chemists, but also for anyone interested in understanding the fundamentals of the quantum world and how these principles govern the behavior and interactions of matter at the microscopic level. The introduction of this concept revolutionized the way scientists understand atomic and molecular structure, and it remains a vital area of study in contemporary physics and chemistry.

HISTORICAL CONTEXT OF PAULI EXCLUSION PRINCIPLE

The Pauli exclusion principle, a cornerstone of quantum mechanics, was introduced by the Austrian physicist Wolfgang Pauli in 1925. It emerged at a time of intense scientific activity and experimentation, when the foundations of classical physics were being questioned and redefined by new discoveries in the field of quantum physics. During the first decades of the 20th century, scientists faced puzzles that could not be explained by existing physical theories, especially with regard to atomic structure and spectroscopy.

Niels Bohr's atomic model, introduced in 1913, was a significant step forward in explaining the emission spectra of hydrogen, but it failed to explain the spectra of more complex atoms or accurately predict the chemical properties of the elements. In this context, Pauli proposed his exclusion principle as a fundamental rule for electrons in an atom, explaining why electrons are distributed in different energy levels or electron shells. The principle was initially based on empirical observation and the need to explain the fine structure of atomic spectra and the periodicity of the chemical properties of the elements in the periodic table.

The introduction of the Pauli exclusion principle was crucial to the later development of quantum mechanics. This principle not only explained the structure of atoms and the formation of molecules, but also provided a solid basis for understanding the stability of matter and the variety of chemical and physical behaviors observed in elements and compounds. In the following decades, the Pauli exclusion principle was integrated into the broader theoretical framework of quantum mechanics, with the formulation of the Schrödinger equation and the development of quantum field theory.

The universal acceptance and application of this principle in physics and chemistry underscores its importance and enduring relevance, constituting one of the fundamental pillars upon which the modern understanding of the universe at the microscopic level is built.

FORMAL DEFINITION OF PAULI EXCLUSION PRINCIPLE

The Pauli exclusion principle is a fundamental rule in quantum mechanics that states that two identical fermions cannot simultaneously occupy the same quantum state within the same system. In mathematical terms, this means that the wave function of a system of identical fermions is antisymmetric, changing sign when two of these particles are exchanged.

APPLICABILITY TO FERMIONIC PARTICLES

Fermions are particles that obey Fermi–Dirac statistics and have half-integer spin ($1/2$, $3/2$, ...). Electrons, protons, neutrons and quarks are examples of fermions and the Pauli exclusion principle applies to all of them. In the context of atoms, the Pauli exclusion principle

explains the structure of electronic energy levels and the unique electronic configurations of elements.

Each quantum state in an atom can be described by a unique set of quantum numbers and, according to the Pauli principle, each state can be occupied by at most one electron (or two, considering opposite spins).

PAULI EXCLUSION PRINCIPLE AND ELECTRONIC CONFIGURATION

The Pauli principle is fundamental to understanding the electronic structure of atoms and therefore the periodic table of elements determining the configuration of electrons in different energy levels and sublevels, which in turn influences the chemical reactivity and properties of the elements.

The way electrons are arranged in atoms and how they can be shared or transferred between atoms to form chemical bonds is essentially determined by the Pauli exclusion principle. This affects the formation of chemical molecules and compounds, their structure and stability.

STABILITY OF MATTER

Matter as we know it could not exist without the Pauli exclusion principle. Electrons would collapse toward the nucleus and atoms would not be able to maintain their structure. The solidity and stability of matter, essential for the formation of complex structures, depend directly on this precept.

The Pauli exclusion principle provides the electron and neutron degeneracy pressure that is crucial for gravitational equilibrium in stars. In white dwarfs, it prevents them from collapsing under their own gravity, while in neutron stars it is the neutron degeneracy that prevents further contraction.

LIMITATIONS OF THE EXCLUSION PRINCIPLE

While the Pauli exclusion principle is fundamental to our understanding of quantum physics and has been validated by a multitude of experiments and observations, there are limitations and contexts in which its applicability must be carefully interpreted.

Although the Pauli exclusion principle is robust within its domain of applicability, theoretical and experimental physics have explored situations that could be interpreted as exceptions or generalizations of the principle.

In particle physics, when strong interactions come into play, such as within atomic nuclei, the properties and behavior of fermions can be influenced by these interactions, which can sometimes complicate and limit the direct application of the exclusion principle.

RELATIONSHIP WITH QUANTUM FIELD THEORY

The Pauli exclusion principle, originally formulated in the context of non-relativistic quantum mechanics, finds a deeper conceptual and formal basis in quantum field theory (QFT). In QFT, particles are described not as isolated entities, but as excitations of underlying fields that span all of space.

In quantum field theory, fermions are treated as quantum fields that obey Fermi–Dirac statistics and are intrinsically antisymmetric. This antisymmetry is a direct manifestation of the Pauli exclusion principle. When two fermions are exchanged, the wave function (or more precisely, the quantum state of the system) acquires a negative sign, which makes it impossible for two identical fermions to occupy the same quantum state.

QFT introduces creation and annihilation operators, which allow us to mathematically describe how particles (fermions, in this case) emerge or disappear from the quantum vacuum. These operators respect the Pauli exclusion principle: a fermion cannot be created in a state that is already occupied by another identical one. The exclusion principle has significant implications for the structure of the vacuum in QFT. The vacuum is not a meaning of nothingness, but a minimum energy state full of quantum activity, where the creation and annihilation of particles occurs constantly.

The Pauli exclusion principle ensures that this vacuum has a complex and rich structure which is fundamental to the stability of the universe. At the quantum level of fields, the Pauli principle is crucial to understanding why matter is stable and why fermionic particles such as electrons and quarks form stable structures such as atoms, molecules and atomic nuclei. This is especially relevant in particle physics and cosmology where matter is studied under the most extreme conditions.

FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

The Pauli exclusion principle is crucial to understanding the electron configuration of atoms and therefore the chemical properties of elements. In physics, it helps explain the stability and structure of matter, from atoms to stars. The implications of the Pauli exclusion principle span atomic structure, molecular formation, the stability of matter, and stellar dynamics.

At the cosmic level, it contributes to the understanding of the evolution and structure of stars, including white dwarfs and neutron stars. In the context of quantum field theory, the Pauli exclusion principle is extended to a broader context, where fermions are treated as antisymmetric quantum fields, strengthening the understanding of fundamental interactions and the stability of the quantum vacuum.

The Pauli exclusion principle influences the development and operation of critical technologies, such as semiconductors and lasers, and has applications in several areas of scientific and technological research.

According to Paul Halpern's text ⁽¹⁴⁾, due to his separation from Käthe Margareth Deppner and the death of his mother, Pauli became an alcoholic and a chain smoker. Pauli had a very strong personality and was relentless in his arguments, which is why he became known as the “conscience of physics” or “God's whip”, nicknames given to him by his friends and scientists of the time. As a result, Pauli began to embarrass himself, which led to a major nervous breakdown. This led his father to propose psychological treatment with the famous psychoanalyst Carl Gustav Jung, in Zurich, with whom Pauli would form a beautiful and great friendship that would last throughout his life. This friendship resulted in an intense exchange of letters and texts written together.

In the book “Pauli and Jung: The Meeting of Two Great Minds”, the author mentions that Jung asked Pauli to use the description of his dreams to write an article, which made Pauli happy to know that his dreams had scientific value and he accepted on the condition of preserving his anonymity. In addition to a relationship with physics, Pauli's dreams also had a strong connection with alchemy. Jung (1991) in his book “Psychology and Alchemy” describes the following: “the material I have consists of more than a thousand dreams and visual impressions of a young man whose scientific training should be emphasized”. In this

same section, Jung maintains Pauli's anonymity and mentions that at first he left it up to his student to start the treatment so that he would not influence the process and that the last 45 dreams, during the treatment, happened with his observation and points out that he did not need to take notes of the interpretations because the patient had a great talent in addition to an excellent academic background. In his thanks, Jung writes: "I am therefore happy to express my gratitude to the "author" for the service he has rendered to science".

Pauli's life is extremely interesting, not only because of his intelligence, but also because of his curious behavior. Pauli was one of the most productive physicists of the golden age of the emergence of the foundations of Quantum Theory, being called by his colleagues "the conscience of Physics". However, much of his life was only made public around the year 2000 with the publication of the most complete biography of him written by fellow physicist Charles Enz, who was Pauli's last assistant and who received all the material left by him from his second wife.

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